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MOSAIC co-creation methodology toolkit

Deliverable No. 4.2

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07/11/2023

Mission-Oriented Swafs to Advance Innovation through Co-creation

Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under
Grant Agreement No. 101006382 - H2020-SwafS-2018-2020 / H2020-SwafS-2020-1

This project has received funding from the European Union's

Executive Summary

This document describes the MOSAIC co-creation methodology. This methodology is particularly fit for the identification of solutions by quadruple helix stakeholders, and it is to be used in Open Innovation contexts where there is a need for shared ideas that can help tackle big challenges (missions) our world is currently changing. The methodology has been tested by two pilot cities - Gothenburg (SE) and Milan (IT), who are part of the Climate Neutral and Smart Cities Mission.

The methodology is presented by describing the co-creation process step-by-step, providing tools which can be used by cities or other stakeholders. The co-creation process consists of three main phases and lasts around 10 to 12 months. In the case of MOSAIC, the entire process was driven by project partners SD and FGB, together with the local city representatives. MOSAIC provided the selected mission cities with full support in the local adaptation of the methodological approach, facilitation, coaching, logistics, ad hoc troubleshooting, interpretation of outcomes and uptake actions.

Deliverable Information

D4.2 – Title of the deliverable	
Deliverable number	4.2
Responsible partner	SD
Due date of deliverable	28/02/2023
First submission date Second submission date	28/02/2023 14/11/2023
Version	Version 2
Authors	Marzia Mazzonetto, Maria Zolotonosa, Carmen Fenollosa, Didier Laval, Fabien Lambert (SD), Angela Simone, Federica Manzoli, Anna Pellizzone (FGB), Mélanie Marcel (SoScience).
Reviewers	Angela Simone (FGB), Maria Zolotonosa, Carmen Fenollosa (SD).
Work package number	4
Work package title	Open Innovation on stage through Co-creation
Work package leader	SD

Dissemination Level		
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium including the Commission Services	<input type="checkbox"/>
PU	Public	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
PP	Restricted to other programme participants, including the Commission Services	<input type="checkbox"/>
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium including the Commission Services	<input type="checkbox"/>

Nature of the Deliverable		
R	Report	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
D	Demonstrator	<input type="checkbox"/>
W	Website, patent filing, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>
O	Other	<input type="checkbox"/>

Partners Involved in the Deliverable

Participant No.	Name of the Organisation	Short Name	Involved
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2	Fondazione Giannino Bassetti	FGB	X
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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	2
Deliverable Information.....	3
Partners Involved in the Deliverable.....	4
Phase 1 – Challenge definition and stakeholder recruitment (3 to 4 months).....	7
Objectives of the phase	8
The process.....	8
What is expected from the process initiator?	9
THE TOOLS.....	9
1. Recommendations on how to choose a co-creation challenge.....	9
2. Structure of Challenge definition workshop(s).....	12
3. Stakeholder mapping guidelines	13
4. Example of stakeholder recruitment open call	14
Phase 2 - The Gathering (1 to 2 months).....	17
Objectives of the phase	17
The process.....	17
What is expected from the process initiator?	17
THE TOOLS.....	18
1. The Gathering – guidelines for facilitation	18
2. Template for idea definition and planning further work (“Idea card”)	20
3. Example of observation template	21
4. Example of evaluation questionnaire.....	22
5. Example of privacy policy form	24
6. Examples of informed consent forms	25
7. Example of ethical guidelines on fair engagement processes.....	28
Phase 3 - Ideation and prototyping (5 to 6 months).....	30
Objectives of the phase	30
The process.....	30
What is expected from the process initiator?	31
THE TOOLS.....	31
1. Example of co-creation general timeline.....	31
2. Example of Idea definition canvas for participants	32
3. Example of Idea definition template for participants.....	32
4. Example of Idea definition facilitation guideline	33
5. Example of storyboard preparation facilitation guideline.....	36
6. Example of light prototyping facilitation guideline	38
7. Example of facilitation guidelines for feedback collection event preparation	41
8. Example of facilitation guide for groups sharing in plenary session.....	43

9.	Example of posters for exchanges among groups.....	44
10.	Example of template for a narrative description of the idea(s) emerged.....	46
11.	Example of Diary for participants/facilitators to record impressions during the process.....	46
12.	Example of Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) for the management of co-created ideas' property rights	47

Phase 1 – Challenge definition and stakeholder recruitment (3 to 4 months)

The first step into co-creation is about choosing which challenge the entire process should focus on. The chosen challenge should be connected to locally identified priorities (such as for example those listed in the cities' 'Climate City Contracts'). The challenge is typically chosen and defined by the city representatives who initiate the process, although it can be also selected through participatory democracy processes such as consultations, involving citizens and other stakeholders. This step is most of the times an internal one; involving external consultants such as experts in co-creation and the process facilitators already at this stage can be very beneficial, as they can support you in how to best formulate the challenge.

TIPS:

- If your chosen challenge is connected to ongoing city initiatives, policies or planning, it will help you turn the co-creation outcomes into something likely to be used and integrated into the city development plans.
- Solutions that will emerge through co-creation might be “complex”, in the sense that they will most likely touch upon responsibilities of various city departments and agencies (i.e., traffic, housing, culture, urban development, budget and finance, citizen affairs, green spaces, etc.). It is important to start your co-creation journey by bringing onboard all the “necessary” city colleagues who can both contribute know-how to the challenge definition, while also playing a role in the co-creation outcomes interpretation and implementation.
- Involving local associations, NGOs, grassroot initiatives, etc. can be key to the success of your stakeholder mapping and recruiting. They know well your territory and they have a huge potential to bring people on board if they believe that the process can have a real impact.

EXAMPLES:

“How to make mobility in the South-West area of the city more sustainable while keeping the same quality of life?” – Gothenburg challenge. Its rationale was based on the following reflections:

- A specific area of the city was identified as particularly interesting to focus on. It is composed of wealthy neighbourhoods, with the highest environmental impact.
- While the city sees reducing cars, spaces for cars, and commuting by car as a key priority, it was decided to formulate the challenge in a neutral way, in order not to bias potential ideas.

“How to inform citizens and city users on air quality so that they can make informed decisions, especially in terms of impacts on their health?”

- A collective challenge that is societally relevant for the whole city was identified and it was framed so that it was interesting for all quadruple-helix groups of stakeholders.
- While the initiators of the process already had in mind an app as potential solution, the question was formulated focusing on the challenge rather than the solution, in order not to bias potential ideas.

Objectives of the phase

- To fine-tune the MOSAIC methodology, identifying minor adaptations to the local context.
- To select the challenge for co-creation together with city representatives – ideally connecting it with the priorities listed in the city’s “Climate City Contract”.
- To get a deep understanding of the context around the chosen challenge (stakeholders to be involved, previous consultations/participatory activities if any, local specificities).
- To launch and promote a call for applications for Quadruple Helix (QH) stakeholders who are interested in getting involved in the co-creation process on the chosen challenge.

The process

1. Defining the challenge

- Online and in-person meetings with city representatives, discussing the methodology and making first steps into the challenge selection.
- Once the challenge topic has been narrowed down, at least two challenge definition workshops with city representatives from various departments.
- The challenge topic should be about something that concerns local QH stakeholders, and it should be framed around a desired outcome, not a potential solution.

2. Call for applications for participants

- Preparation, publication and promotion of the call for onboarding of QH stakeholders.
- Key aspects to think about when building the registration form: data management informed consent, relevant information to collect about potential participants (including motivations to join, demographic aspects, etc.), time availability to join the process kick-off meeting (The Gathering) and further group work during the entire duration of the co-creation.
- Implementation of actions aimed at promoting the call by actively reaching out to specific stakeholders and inviting them to get involved (i.e., in collaboration with local associations).
- Development of criteria for the selection of participants (in case you have more people registered than your set limit). In the case of MOSAIC, the number of participants was limited to 50 persons (in total, covering all stakeholder groups).

3. On-the-ground support activities for inclusion

- Map and Identify stakeholders who most likely will not apply to the open call for various reasons, including but not limited to lack of time and/or resources, lack of motivation, lack of trust in potential impacts, etc.
- Contact and arrange meetings (in person, by phone or video-call) with such stakeholders to assess their views on the chosen challenges, and ask for their reasons for not getting involved in the process.

- Implement options that will allow their participation or at least their inputs to be taken into account, such as exchanges with them by phone or video-call at various stages of the process, or an invitation to at least one process activity where a support system is set up to allow for their presence.

4. Selection process

- While the call is still open, set-up a Selection Committee composed of city representatives, supporting methodology/facilitation partners, and any other type of expert you might see fit.
- Once the call is closed, invite the Selection Committee to choose participants for the process (suggested: 30-50 people), based on pre-defined criteria.
- Ensure a balanced representation of stakeholder groups and areas of expertise. Inclusivity aspects should also be considered (such as gender balance).

What is expected from the process initiator?

- To participate in the requested workshops and mobilise other departments / stakeholders if and when needed, based on the chosen challenge.
- To take responsibility and ownership of the selected challenge.
- To define a clear commitment towards the uptake of co-creation outcomes which can be transparently communicated to participants from the start.
- To be in charge of the active promotion of the call for applications.
- To have a dedicated member of staff for weekly contact/Interactions with the MOSAIC team (applicable to all phases).
- To ensure the call for action meets the city internal processes and requirements (procurement etc..).

THE TOOLS

1. Recommendations on how to choose a co-creation challenge

Introduction

This tool describes the process leading to the identification and definition of a challenge which can be addressed through co-innovation. The challenge definition should always go hand in hand with a process involving all concerned stakeholders, also called “co-design” phase. Through co-design activities such as consultations, agenda-setting, climate assemblies and more, Quadruple Helix (QH) stakeholders are engaged in a process that leads to the identification of shared challenges.

For example: a city is in the process of preparing its strategic plan to achieve climate neutrality by 2030. Citizens, civil society organizations, researchers, innovators and companies are involved in a wide consultation process through various approaches. An online consultation is made available for all citizens to express their ideas. Workshops are organised involving each stakeholder group separately, around the main question of “Let’s imagine our city in 2030”. Stakeholders are asked to express first what they think should change and how they envisage

their city in 2030, then they are led to express ideas and priorities which could make it happen. Priorities and ideas emerging from the consultative processes are matched with existing strategic policy agendas, and potentially further discussed with stakeholders with the aim of identifying common ground. Shared strategic priorities therefore emerge and are integrated in new policies and action plans.

In the specific case of MOSAIC and the Climate Neutral and Smart Cities mission, the co-design phase corresponds to the cities' work towards the preparation of their Climate City Contracts. MOSAIC pilot cities have already done this work in the past, leading to the identification of strategic priorities for climate neutrality within their own local contexts.

Key points

Look at your Climate City Contracts through the lenses of multi-stakeholder engagement.

The first step in the challenge identification is therefore to carefully look at existing Climate City Contracts (CCC) or other strategic plans which will be used as a basis for the Mission, and establish which are the challenges that were particularly attracting stakeholders' attention and motivation during the co-design phase. Alternatively, you can identify them based on your own experience of your local context. Attracting stakeholders' attention does not necessarily mean choosing a challenge on which everyone agrees.

For example, citizens might be advocating for a city with less cars and more green spaces, innovators, companies and universities might be pushing towards electric cars and related infrastructure and technology advancements, while local businesses and associations, although aware of the importance of reducing pollution from cars, are also concerned about the impact on their activities and revenues. This is a typical broad challenge which could be interesting for you to focus on and to identify a specific mission project within it for your co-innovation process.

Large or small-scale challenges?

Co-innovation allows you to address a large variety of challenges, even broad ones, although there are several elements you should consider when picking one. The first and most obvious one is your availability in terms of efforts, support and budget you can dedicate to the process you want to implement. Large-scale co-creation processes can be time consuming and a bit costly - they require more efforts than consultations and other co-design activities. The infrastructure required should also be considered. A less obvious aspect regards commitment: as a city representative, if you initiate a co-innovation process, you should reflect upon what it is concretely possible for you to do to support the uptake of what will emerge from it. The choice of your challenge will therefore necessarily require a negotiation process between your city's political agenda and stakeholders' identified priorities.

For example, co-developing solutions towards better public transport options that will motivate more and more people to change their commuting habits is a challenge that concerns the entire city. But different neighbours or specific areas of your cities might face different challenges. You can therefore either set up a city-wide co-innovation process while still ensuring that local working groups address specific contexts, having major stakeholders involved (such as private companies managing public transport systems or producers of public transport means). Or you might want to start by focusing on specific target groups or areas of

your city, as test beds for further developments, while still having large key players involved. It might also be easier to convince them to get involved in a smaller case co-innovation process to start with.

Your challenge formulation matters

When defining your challenge, it is key to a co-innovation process to provide a formulation of the problem that allows all participants (and therefore all stakeholders groups) to feel like there is something in it that concerns them and on which they can have a say, and therefore not to miss the views of certain groups. If you are addressing a broad challenge like air pollution and you want to focus on a specific source of contamination, you should make sure that relevant stakeholder groups will not refuse or be reluctant to get involved in the process just because they feel like it's something too far away from them.

For example, in the case certain specific types of industries (i.e., manufacturing, power plants, etc.) or a specific sector (i.e., tourism) are a big source of pollution in your city, citizens or other types of local actors might feel discouraged to get engaged and provide their contribution due to frustration towards whether anything will ever really change. Framing the challenge in a way that highlights the potential positive impacts for all the co-innovation and its implementation is key to engaging stakeholders. We recommend to frame challenges around the social or environmental outcomes instead of framing it around technical solutions or options.

Keep in mind your final aim

In a co-innovation process, your desired outputs are tangible outcomes, such as technologies, services or new organisational structures.

Overall, your challenge should:

- Be broad enough and always have a clear link to your Climate City Contracts. It should not be a merely technical challenge (for example, 3D printing is not an eligible topic).
- Besides addressing challenges recognised by the scientific community and supported by scientific data, the challenge should also have a strong link with societal needs that you have identified through your co-design phase.
- Ideally, the challenge should foster solutions that respond to technical, economic, social and environmental issues.

Guiding questions

- Within your CCC, which are the priorities / challenges which resonate the most to key stakeholders in your city?
- Do you know your stakeholders' views on your chosen challenge? If so, can you list some of them?
- Is your challenge addressing societal needs?
- How likely will you be able to mobilise 4H stakeholders in a co-creation process around your chosen challenge?
- Is your challenge range (from very small/localised to very broad and lengthy) adapted to your availability in terms of efforts and budget?

- As a public authority, what can you “commit to” regarding your chosen challenge? If not a formal commitment, what actions do you think you will be able to take / support in case satisfying ideas emerge from the co-creation process?
- What do you think could emerge from a co-creation process around your chosen challenge?

2. Structure of Challenge definition workshop(s)

These workshops can be held online and last around 2 hours each. We suggest two workshops, but there can be more sessions if needed. We suggest to regularly plan energizers or similar activities to keep participants involved. In case that participants are not familiar yet with the methodology and the process, we suggest introducing those before working on the challenge definition.

Suggested activities:

- Presentation of the methodology (overall process) - focus on what is expected by the initiator(s) and participants, and stimulate reflections on challenges that might be faced.
- Presentation of the challenge rationale.
- Time for comments and QA.
- Familiarising with the current context. For example, invite participants to share experiences, and citizen engagement activities, that they think can be relevant to inform or influence the chosen challenge.
- Individually brainstorm on a strategic priority you want to tackle with the co-creation.
- Share with others how your idea for a strategic challenge fits with the “challenge rationale”, and why you think this challenge can be addressed with the MOSAIC co-creation approach.
- Prioritise propositions to identify the preferred one.
- Check the chosen challenge against the rationale.
- Once your challenge is chosen, focus on agreeing on common goals for the co-creation process. For this, you can use an ideal scenario/visioning exercise, which will also help you identify what goals you want to have for your co-creation process.
- Use a problem definition canvas to formulate and re-frame the challenge.
- Define your commitment (especially in terms of up-take of co-creation results).
- Decide who should be involved in this process, who is key to solving the challenge?

<p>What is the key social problem/need you are addressing and why is it important?</p> <p><i>Explain the reasons why the problem/need is important.</i></p>	<p>What social/cultural factors shape this problem?</p> <p><i>Sociocultural factors are customs, lifestyles and values that characterise a community. You could think about esthetics, education, language, law, politics, religion, technology, material culture, values and attitudes.</i></p>	<p>Who is it a problem important/relevant for?</p>	<p>What evidence do you have that this is a significant problem?</p> <p><i>You might also want to think about the stakeholders and their opinion about the problem.</i></p>	<p>Can you think of the problem in a different way? Can you reframe it?</p>
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You are now ready to start your stakeholder mapping in relation to the challenge.

4. Example of stakeholder recruitment open call

Towards sustainable mobility in Gothenburg

(This is the text of the call that was published to launch the co-creation process in Gothenburg. It was published on the city website and promoted through several channels, including social media, local radios, etc.).

Göteborg is on the path to becoming Carbon neutral by 2030. However, to do so it needs for all of us to work together to devise solutions that are efficient and functional for everyone. The way we move around has a great impact on the carbon emissions of our cities. At the same time, mobility shapes our lifestyles, our comfort, and the choices we make every day. Decreasing emissions generated by urban mobility will affect our lifestyle and will require close collaboration towards creative solutions.

Göteborgs Stad is inviting participants to this collaborative open innovation programme aimed at creating new partnerships to design shared solutions. The goal is to come up with creative ideas to reducing carbon emissions while addressing citizens' needs regarding the way they move around.

The context

The most recent IPCC report is clear about the dangers posed by the climate crisis and the need to act. Cities need to play a pivotal role in achieving climate neutrality. Although they take up only 4% of the EU's land area, cities are home to 75% of EU citizens, 65% of the world's energy consumption and account for more than 70% of global CO2 emission. Urban mobility accounts for 40 % of all CO2 emissions from road transport and up to 70% of other pollutants from transport.

We want to be able to reach climate neutrality by 2030, therefore, we must achieve an unprecedented transition, making a great effort to transform our cities.

Gothenburg, alongside 111 other European cities, has committed to becoming climate-neutral, and the city's new environmental and climate programme aims to reduce its climate impact to "close to zero" by 2030, with a view to reaching a zero footprint as quickly as possible. This means that Gothenburg will need to reduce emissions in its geographical area by at least 10.3% per year and consumption-based emissions by at least 7.6% per year.

The challenge we invite you to address

The transition to sustainable urban mobility is generally acknowledged as one of the major challenges for the future. With an urban area with around 1 million inhabitants and only 570.000 city dwellers, Gothenburg needs to ensure the mobility of a big number of commuters. The main question we will focus on is:

How can we co-develop inclusive mobility that meets personal needs, is affordable, comfortable and reliable?

The process

Our goal is to develop solutions with and for citizens, local businesses and public representatives to support sustainable changes to the way we move around the city. We need solutions where the different players understand each other's preferences and priorities by

working together along the same journey. Successful collaboration will increase our potential to develop creative solutions, think laterally and experiment with “out of the box” ideas.

Together, we will find concrete solutions to questions such as:

- What would make our life better mobility-wise?
- What could fit your mobility needs, while also decreasing your carbon footprint?
- What would improve the user-friendliness and aesthetics of mobility in the neighbourhood?

The first step in the process will be the gathering, where all selected participants will get the chance to meet, get to know each other and form co-creation teams. This event takes place during (... - add dates of the Gathering).

All participants need to be available for those two half-days. For the whole process participants should be available to take part in (...) meetings until (...) and work with their teams in between on developing their projects. None of the co-creation activities will require a full-day commitment, they will have a duration of between one and four hours and will be organised at a time that is suitable for most.

Who can apply?

- NGOs / Non-profit organisations
- Citizens, civic organisations, communities
- Research Organisations/Academia
- Industrial/Innovation Companies
- Start-up / SME / Social enterprises
- Public/governmental organisation

All applicants are welcome and we invite actors with different backgrounds: companies, start-ups, researchers from all fields, citizens/community groups, neighbour's associations, commuters, social entrepreneurs, engineers, designers, economists, fleet managers, environmental NGOs, shop owners, anyone with mobility wishes and needs willing to be part of this change.

The co-creation process will focus on the south-west commuter belt of Gothenburg. We particularly invite participants who for any reasons frequently use the road 158 from Järnbrottsmotet until Brottkärrsmotet, which is the focus area for the co-creation process. If you feel you have any kind of direct or indirect experience on this area, even if not directly connected to it, please apply.

Selection criteria

We expect to involve around 50 individuals including organisation representatives in the process. In case a selection will be needed, we will choose participants based on ensuring a fair balance of:

- Representatives of the above-mentioned categories.
- Know-how and views represented.
- Motivations and interest in the topic.
- Willingness to work in a partnership and to collaborate with others.

Benefits/What's in it for me?

- Let your ideas be part of the ongoing work towards a climate neutral city by 2030.
- Improve mobility services in your city.
- Meet new people and build impactful collaborations.
- Make your voices, views and needs heard.
- Access to a group of international open innovation experts.
- Learn complementary approaches and skills.
- And above all, contribute to making your community a healthier place to live.

The 3 best collaborative projects that will emerge will be offered technical and operational support for up to 6 months to help develop and prototype their ideas (multi-stakeholder coordination, design thinking, intellectual property, project management, fundraising, etc.). The 3 best projects will also be shown how to build clear visions of how their proposed solutions will scale and contribute to solving the challenge – an essential element for mobilising further support from the city.

Commitment

The city of Gothenburg is the initiator of this programme. It is being supported by the EU-funded MOSAIC project and in particular its coordinator, Stickydot srl, a Brussels-based collective that shapes research and innovation through multi-stakeholder engagement and co-creation.

The city administration shares the objective and commits to supporting the programme. It will both take part in the process and closely follow each of the projects being developed by the three selected teams. It will assess all projects in terms of scalability, innovation, effectiveness and implementation. Since the result is created by local stakeholders the city of Gothenburg will value the results highly. Each result will be considered for further financial support or assisted into the decision-making process of the city.

Application form

1. Name and contact details.
2. Describe who you are, and in case you have an affiliation, your organisation.
3. What motivates you to take part in this programme?
4. Describe your know-how and/or daily life experience in the field of mobility and what you could bring to the challenge we are trying to solve. (Know-how does not mean that one needs to be an expert in the topic, e.g. if you are from a Neighbour's association in a certain area, you have expertise in the local area: its lifestyle, the habits, the problems, etc.).
5. Do you have any existing project idea in the field of mobility? If so describe.
6. What do you think you can benefit from collaborating and building partnerships with others?
7. Are you available to attend the first meeting, called the Gathering) on (...)?

Phase 2 - The Gathering (1 to 2 months)

The Gathering is a day-long participatory workshop (it can also be run over two half days), where all selected and recruited quadruple helix stakeholders will come together first the first time. It is a key moment in the process, and it has two ambitious goals. First, to make participants connect, enjoy themselves and openly share their experience around the chosen topic. The atmosphere created at the Gathering will be key to motivating participants to stay involved in the co-creation process. The second goal is to make the participants gather around collaborative ideas, through a carefully facilitated process.

Objectives of the phase

- To bring together and onboard city's QH stakeholders.
- To select co-creation teams that will address the challenge.
- To support them in working together toward the objective.
- To facilitate networking and getting-to-know each other opportunities.
- To support them in working together toward the objective.

The process

1. The Gathering

- The first big gathering of all selected participants and the organising team is the moment of formation of co-creation teams and the kick-off of the co-creation work.
- The objectives of The Gathering are two-fold: (i) for participants to get to know each other (and better understand each other's expertise) and form co-creation teams, (ii) To further assess stakeholders' views on the challenge and help them find common ground.
- Activities taking place during The Gathering: i.e. participatory sessions (starting by working in separate stakeholder groups), mini-ideation sessions, speed-dating, social moments.

2. Launch of group work – idea identification

- All formed teams go through a facilitated process to kick-off their work on the selection and identification of their idea.
- The groups then work on their own milestones and deliver a draft idea (vision) within a short timeframe (i.e. a month) Based on that vision the Selection Committee selects 3 teams to be actively supported in the co-creation process.

What is expected from the process initiator?

- Logistical support in the organisation of The Gathering.
- Clear commitment and ownership of the programme (e.g. support offered to the most interesting ideas or other types of commitment).
- (ideally) The city should ideally provide a place for the participants to meet throughout the whole process and access to city resources that might be needed.

- MOSAIC commits to supporting 3 teams in the co-creation process; the city needs to decide whether they want to do something with extra-groups.

THE TOOLS

1. The Gathering – guidelines for facilitation

You can either run the Gathering over one or two days, depending on the context.

If you decide to go for one day, in second part you can decide to skip the phases “Getting to know each other” (beginning of Part 2 in this guideline).

Objectives of the Gathering

- To bring together for the first time all selected participants and the organising team.
- For participants, to get to know each other and better understand each other’s expertise, experiences, needs and ideas.
- To further assess stakeholders’ views on the challenge and facilitate activities that will lead them to identify common ground and shared ideas.
- To form 3 groups (co-creation teams) that will be working separately on ideas and potential solutions to address the specific challenge.
- To kick-off of the co-creation work.

Structure

PART 1 (3 to 4 hours)

00:00-00:20 Welcome and introduction

Quick icebreaker: the lead facilitator, without introducing herself/himself, asks the participants to say one word they associate with the topic of the challenge – words are introduced in a Sli.do by a notetaker in real time, forming a word cloud that is projected on a screen. Brief introduction about the challenge, the aims of the co-creation process and timeline and explanation of the framework (how we will work together) and code of conduct.

00:20-01:00 Contextualisation

Short pitches by external speakers aimed at providing a brief, neutral introduction on existing data, studies, geographic data, etc. regarding the challenge topic. Pitches in the case of the MOSAIC pilot cities also focused on making more explicit the links between how the co-creation process can contribute to the city priorities (e.g., its Climate City Contract).

01:00-02:00 Barriers and concerns (*this part can be skipped in case of limited time availability*)

Exercise 1: participants are provided with an A3 hand-out and invited to draw on it following a topic specific question. Participants are then invited one by one to explain what they have been drawing to the rest of the group. This exercise is aimed at breaking the ice and getting participants to focus on the challenge topic. It is also helpful to get an understanding of their current habits around the topic.

Exercise 2: participants are asked to think about challenges / barriers / concerns they encounter, feel or perceive in relation to the topic of the co-creation. They are given a few minutes to write on post-its. The facilitator then asks them to share what they wrote, and clusters post-its on a flip chart.

02:00-02:15 Break

02:15-03:00 Visions and opportunities

Exercise 3: Participants are asked to focus on a question that makes them think about their vision of the future in relation to the challenge, and what changes are needed in order to get there. Example of a question: How will the city look like in 2030 in relation to the challenge? What will be the main observed transformations?

The facilitator explains that the co-creation project should contribute to shared desired objectives, and that these objectives can change and be revisited during the course of the programme.

Participants are invited to write their visions and expected transformations on post-its (one per post-it). The facilitator then asks them to share what they wrote, and clusters post-its on a flip chart.

03:00-03:20 Sharing of outcomes

A representative of each stakeholder group (ideally not the facilitators but a member of the group) shares main outcomes of exercise 2 (barriers and concerns) and exercise 3 (visions and opportunities).

3:20-3:30 Closing and introduction of Part 2

Part 2 (3 to 4 hours)

00:00-00:20 Welcome and recap

Welcome back and agenda of the day. Reminder of main outcomes of Part 1, highlighting potential common ground.

00:20-00:50 Getting to know each other – part 1 (*this part can be skipped in case of limited time availability*)

Activity: the off-line social network. Participants are invited to make a sketch of themselves on a piece of paper, write their name, and then stick the drawing on a big paper on a wall. Participants are then invited to split into pairs and have a few minutes to find at least one thing (possibly not work-related) that they share or have in common. They are invited to draw lines on the paper connecting their sketches in case they find something in common. The same process is repeated at least 4 or 5 times, depending on timing.

00:50-01:20 Getting to know each other – part 2 (*this part can be skipped in case of limited time availability*)

Activity: the crazy 6s. Participants are split into mixed-stakeholder groups (6 people per group). They are invited to think about crazy ideas related to the challenges. They are provided a hand-out where they are asked to very quickly draw one idea per minute (6 minutes in total)

for 6 ideas). Participants are then invited to share with the group their top two ideas, one by one.

01:20-01:35 Break

01:35-02:30 Forming groups

Participants are invited to write on a piece of paper an idea in relation to the challenge (i.e. solution, product, service). These should be formulated in the form of “My name is ... and my proposition is...”. The facilitator reminds participants about what already discussed so far, and previous exercises. The papers are then stuck to a white wall. Each participant is invited to briefly share their idea with the group. Not all participants have to make a proposition, the facilitator explains that it is ok not to have one.

The facilitator clusters ideas as much as possible, with the aim to try and reduce them to three groups. If not possible, the facilitators give three stickydots to each participant and asks them to vote for their three favourite propositions (or clusters of propositions). Only the three top voted propositions are used in the next steps (the other propositions are kept for potential use in the future, in case one of the top-three ones does not move forward).

Participants are invited to go stand next to the proposition out of the three that they would like the most to work on in the future. Three groups form. The facilitators invited them to look at the colour of their badges, and check whether all four colours are more or less equally represented in their group. If not, participants are invited to kindly move to their second favourite proposition, explaining that groups have to be balanced and inviting them to be collaborative and volunteer to move if needed. Working groups are therefore shaped (ideally no more than 10 participants per group).

02:30-03:20

The three groups are invited to gather and sit separately (one facilitator per group). The groups are provided with a template of points they have to work together on:

- (20 minutes) discuss together the concept of their co-creation proposition that emerged in the previous exercise, explaining that it can evolve into something different than originally stated (the facilitator makes sure all voices are heard). When agreeing on a proposition, participants are invited to think and write in the template about its expected transformations (desired goals); the barriers/challenges/concerns it addresses; the envisioned solution (in a very draft form); and a “wow sentence” about it (its starting/selling point).
- (20 minutes) groups are invited to plan how they want to work together. On the template, they fill together information on a) agreeing on at least one date to meet next; b) what are their needs in terms space, facilitation, tools, etc. c) distribution of roles and responsibilities; d) how to stay in touch (communication channels to be used).

03:20-03:30 Wrap-up and closing

2. Template for idea definition and planning further work (“Idea card”)

As a group you should try and agree on your initial idea. After this meeting you will get the chance to revisit the idea and even change it completely if needed. You have 20 minutes for this exercise.

Idea definition

1. Challenge What challenge are you addressing?	2. Solution If the problem was solved, what would it look like?
3. Idea Describe your idea.	4. Value What is the unique selling point of your idea? What is its “wow” effect?

Planning future work

What roles are important to have in your team? Who can be in charge of what?
What are your needs in terms of meeting spaces, tools, further support?
What communication channel will you use to keep in touch? Who will set it up?
When will you meet next to advance the work?
How can we contact your team?

3. Example of observation template

This template can be used by participants taking part in the Gathering as silent observers, to support the collecting observations.

Aims	
Aims of the observation	Please collect here information about: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholder views on the challenge. • Differences in opinions and common ground. • Group dynamics.
Topic	
Observer	Form filled in by:

Stakeholders	<p>As far as you know:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How many participants took part in the event? • Which stakeholder group was the largest/the smallest? • What is your general view of the group? • Were any important stakeholders / participants missing? • Were the participants complementary to each other? • Were they mostly aligned with peers from same stakeholder group? If not, can you briefly elaborate?
Atmosphere	<p>Can you describe the atmosphere during the meeting in three key words? E.g., good / tensions / collaborative other...</p> <p>Can you briefly elaborate?</p>
Evaluative questions	<p>What went well? Please describe a situation (e.g., what, who, what were the outcomes, why do you think it went well?):</p> <p>What can be improved? How and why? Please describe:</p> <p>What remark or discussion comes to mind immediately? Please describe:</p>
About the event	<p>Can you describe a situation that stood out in a positive way? Please describe:</p>
	<p>Can you describe a situation that needs more attention next time? Please describe:</p>
Dynamics of the engagement	<p>Was there any common ground/common views/consensus that you noticed?</p> <p>Was there one or more contributions of a participant which stood out in a positive or negative way? Please describe:</p> <p>What was the (main) challenge the participants talked about during the event?</p>
Suggestions	<p>What suggestion for improvement would you – as an observer – give for the next steps?</p>
Summary	<p>Can you provide a short summary of the event with help of a few keywords or sentences?</p>

4. Example of evaluation questionnaire

Thank you for your participation in The Gathering. To help us analyze our practices and improve future activities, please answer these few questions.

What is the color of your badge? (*each stakeholder group has been previously assigned a colour*)

Blue Red Yellow Green

On a scale of 1-10 (1 being the lowest and 10 being the highest) ...

1- How satisfied are you with what you gained (either personally, as an institution or as resulting impact) in this gathering?

2- Do you consider your time was well-spent by participating?

3- Do you feel your concerns were treated fairly compared to concerns of other participants?

4- Following The Gathering, do you think you have a better understanding of the concerns of other stakeholders (e.g. private actors, citizens, civil servants, etc.)?

5- Following The Gathering, did you include other type of participants' (e.g. private actors, citizens, civil servants, etc.) point of view to inform your perspective on the topic?

6- When you had divergent opinions, do you feel that the process helped you address these conflicts?

5. Example of privacy policy form

Privacy Policy (according to Articles 13 and 14 EU Regulation 679/2016, "Regulation")

1. Data controller

(name and address of entity), in its capacity as Data Controller (hereinafter '...') by virtue of its role as co-implementer of the ... process in activities in cooperation with the ..., agrees to protect the privacy of those who provide their personal data through this notice ('Notice').

In general, all information provided by you will be processed by ... in a lawful, fair and transparent manner. To this end, and as further described below, ... takes into consideration internationally recognised principles governing the processing of Personal Data, such as purpose limitation, storage space limitation, data minimisation, data quality and confidentiality.

For more details about the processing of your Personal Data, please see the Extended Privacy Policy at: ...

In addition, you may write to: ...

2. Types of data subject to processing

The personal data processed by ... are first name, last name, contact details (...).

3. Purpose, optionality and legal basis of data processing

The personal data described above will be processed for the following purposes: ...

- a) Activities related to participation in the InformAria co-creation and social research project in collaboration with the Municipality of Milan in the context of .;
- b) fulfilment of the obligations laid down in laws, regulations and EU legislation, as well as provisions issued by authorities empowered to do so by law and by supervisory and control bodies ("compliance").

The processing of personal data for the purposes described above is always optional but, in the absence of consent, ... will not be able to fulfil any of these purposes.

For the purposes of participation in the in-person and online meetings of the ... process (letter a of this information notice), this purpose also includes the publication of the images/recordings of the participants during the workshops (the setting up and use of which is to be considered free of charge) for the sole purpose of documenting the events themselves and their possible dissemination via the web in ...'s internet and social accounts and through communication channels connected with the process. The legal basis for the aforementioned purpose is consent (Art. 6 n.1 lett a GDPR).

For 'compliance' purposes (letter b of this notice), the legal basis for the processing is a legal obligation to which is subject.

4. Recipients and transfer of personal data

Personal data may be shared with:

- natural persons authorised by ... to process personal data after signing an authorisation agreement for the processing of personal data (e.g. employees, collaborators and system administrators of FGB);
- parties that typically act as data controllers (e.g. companies providing IT services, consultants, etc.);
- subjects, bodies or authorities to whom it is mandatory to communicate personal data due to legal provisions, orders of authorities with respect to compliance purposes (e.g. Authorities and Supervisory and Control Bodies).

... does not transfer your aforementioned personal data outside the European Economic Area.

5. Personal data storage

The personal data provided for the purposes set out in point 3, letters a), b), will be stored by the data controller within the terms of the law, exclusively for the time required for the purposes indicated.

5. Rights that may be exercised by the data subject

You have the right to request from ..., at any time, access to, rectification or erasure of your personal data or to object to their processing. You also have the right to request the restriction of processing in the cases provided for by Article 18 of the Regulation, as well as to obtain in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format the data concerning you, in the cases provided for by Article 20 of the Regulation.

You may exercise these rights by writing to ... at the following address: ...

In any case, you always have the right to file a complaint with the competent supervisory authority (Personal Data Protection Authority), pursuant to Article 77 of the Regulation, if you believe that the processing of your data is contrary to the legislation in force.

Having read the above information, I, the undersigned:

(Name and Last name)

I consent to the processing of my personal data for purposes related to participation in the in-person and online meetings of the InformAria process within the ...

I do not consent to processing for purposes related to participation in the in-person and online meetings of the ... process as part of the ... process (in which case it will not be possible to participate in the events)

(Date)*

(Signature)*

* DATE AND SIGNATURE LEGIBLE

6. Examples of informed consent forms

EXAMPLE 1

Declaration of Data Protection and Informed Consent for participation in activities that are part of the ... co-creation process.

Description of the process: (....)

Name and contact details of the data controller ("study leader"): (..)

Type of Data collected

During the ... co-creation process personal data will be collected. This includes: your name, contact information (email, phone number), occupation, professional background, and your personal opinions. Furthermore, photos, as well as audio and video recordings of the sessions will be taken.

Participation in the pilot

Participation in this pilot requires multiple workshops and meetings of various duration. Two workshops take place on Further in person and online meetings and workshops are held between ..., for a maximum of ... activities. Risks of participation should be negligible, but it is always possible that sensitive opinions or confidential information could be shared inadvertently. Participation in the study is always voluntary: you may choose not to respond to any question or to discuss a particular topic, and you can terminate your participation at any time.

Usage of your Data

The data generated within this process (interview / focus group / workshop / forum / meeting / interview) will be used for This includes the processing for research purposes and dissemination activities as well as reporting on project progress to The data generated will also be used by ... to further support ideas that will emerge from the process.

Data Recipients

Data recipients are:

Processing and Storing of your Data

For the analysis of the co-creation process, audio-recording, note-taking and collection of written information through post-its and alike will be performed. Your data will be stored Due to requirements of ..., the data collected might be stored until up to ... years after the end of the process. When storing data, ... researchers will erase personal data such as phone numbers and emails. Processed anonymised person-specific data might become part of publications (including scientific papers) and other dissemination materials. In the ... co-creation activities, you will state personal opinions which might be critical for you to some extent. While your names and screenshots may be published, we will protect the anonymity of personal opinions. Therefore, any personal opinions will be anonymized so that no relation can be established to the personal data of the participant. In addition, you have the explicit right to not answer a specific question. Your data will not be sent to third parties. The sole purpose of storing your data is for research, dissemination and policy support.

Your rights

During the ... co-creation activities, you are always free to not answer a specific question or leave without any consequences. If you would like to address a question or an issue, please feel free to do so. Furthermore, you shall have the right to access, to rectify, to erase, to restrict the processing and the right to data portability as granted in GDPR Article 15 -22. In addition you have the right to object to the processing of your personal data. You can also withdraw your consent at any time, by contacting us without any consequences. The withdrawal of consent does not affect the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal. If you are of the opinion that your data is processed unlawfully, you have the right to file a complaint with the data protection authority. Upon request your local supervisory authority will provide you information on exercising your right according to Article 57(e) GDPR. In order to exercise your rights, please contact

Dissemination of Results

The data generated will be used for ... related research purposes in the field of co-creation and open innovation, and dissemination materials. This includes deliverables, publications, reports, booklets and commentaries, policy briefs, blog posts, web pages, social media, journal articles and books.

Code of Conduct

Participation in ... is meant to be as agreeable and pleasant as possible for all those involved. Therefore, all participants agree to respect the following rules:

- Racism and discrimination: racist comments, discrimination on the basis of sex, age, or disability, publication of racist or sexist pictures and insulting persons are strictly banned.
- ... may not be misused for political, religious or advertising purposes.
- Infringements of copyright laws are not permitted.
- All participants' conduct should always be appropriate and never offensive or deprecating.

Fair rewarding

By taking part in the ... co-creation process, participants agree to respect the Ethical Guidelines These guidelines can be found below. A printed copy of the Ethical Guidelines is available upon registration. It can also be requested by email by sending a message to

Consent

After having stated these general conditions and rules, we are looking forward to a good cooperation and positive project results. We would like to thank you in advance for your participation in the project. The undersigned declare that they understand and consent to the conditions and rules of Both parties receive a copy of this declaration of consent.

I hereby release ... and any of its associated or affiliated institutions, their directors, officers, agents, employees and customers from all claims of every kind on account of such use.

Participant's name :

Contact's name:

Participant's signature:

Contact's signature:

Location, day/month/year

Location, day/month/year

EXAMPLE 2

You have been invited to participate in the ... co-creation (participatory innovation) process, which will take place - both face-to-face and online - between (... add start and end date), as part of the social research project / co-creation process

A co-creation process involves actors from different fields (business, associations, research and governance) working together, sharing their experiences, skills and points of view in order to develop a concrete solution capable of responding to a common challenge. In this specific case, through your participation, you will help us to develop (...).

The process will take place over several meetings, some of which will be audio-recorded so that the conversations between you and the other participants can be transcribed and analysed at a later date for the sole purposes of the ... project.

The transcripts of the dialogues that will take place and the ideas that will emerge will not contain your name. The results of this process, as well as being used to develop a solution to (...), may be used for scientific publication in aggregate form; therefore, the contributions of (individual) people will not be identifiable.

Furthermore, in order to protect the confidentiality of the participants, by consenting to participate, you agree to ensure that the content of the discussions that will take place during the meetings in which you will participate will not be shared in any way with parties who were not involved. The same will apply to all participants.

Your participation is voluntary. Please feel free to withdraw from the process at any time. Should you decide to withdraw from the process, it will not be possible to remove any contributions you may have made before withdrawing.

Through this informed consent form, you have received complete and truthful information about this research project and its aims.

By participating in ...'s in-presence and online meetings you agree to take part in the co-creation and social research process described above.

Your participation is free of charge. The intellectual property of the proposals that will be conceived and potentially realised, even outside the (...) project process, remains exclusively in the hands of the creators (members of the working groups) and is not patentable. While it remains shared between the members of the working groups, further reflections on the intellectual property of the solutions developed and how to recognise each member's contribution can be carried out by the participants themselves during the process.

Signature (legible)

Date (legible)

7. Example of ethical guidelines on fair engagement processes

- No co-creation process should be set up without a prior shared reflection on intellectual property rights and the potential profits distribution of its outputs. Especially in negotiating with private sector representatives their participation in the process, this element should be highlighted and discussed before the start of the co-creation path. The involvement of the private sector in co-creation processes represents both a

challenge (e.g., in case of unfair appropriation of shared ideas) and an opportunity. Having representatives of the private sector involved from the start should be mediated by co-creation initiators by fostering an open conversation on potential rewards that can be acceptable to them.

- The definition of intellectual property rights and potential profits distribution can be achieved through a top-down process (i.e. the public administration running the processes defines and informs participants about what is achievable and whom it belongs to) or, even better, a bottom-up approach (i.e. all participants are involved in the definition of rewarding expectations, ahead of the start of the process).
- Public administrations often dispose of entire units/departments dedicated to managing and strengthening the collaboration with (and governance of) the private sector. It is advisable to involve representatives of such offices in co-creation processes. They can both support the exploitation of co-creation ideas through city-owned channels (e.g. business incubators) and mediate discussions on ownership issues with private companies involved in the process. With them, while looking at sectors in which this kind of discussion is gaining momentum (open data), explore a new way of reconfiguring products and services for the public good as “public products”, focusing less on who are the idea/products conception holders and more on the purposes for which the product can be used.
- Creative commons forms of ownership are ideal, even though only sometimes possible. Shared ownership of outcomes should always be preferred. When not possible, due to the need to privatise innovative ideas, other forms of reward should be adopted, such for example shareholding or free access to products and services for those who contributed to their development.
- Transparency is key. Whether any form of reward is considered or not, it is important to inform participants from the start about the conditions of their participation in the process. This should be clearly stated in informed consent forms and explained to them.
- Communication actions to inform co-creation participants on how their contribution has been used and finalised is of utmost importance. While planning a co-creation process, define means and channels for follow-up activities.

Phase 3 - Ideation and prototyping (5 to 6 months)

Once groups have formed during the Gathering, the next step is to provide them with the necessary support to keep working together. Typically, groups will meet at least a couple of times per month (or even once a week, depending on their availability). They will start working on the very embryonic collaborative idea(s) that have emerged during the gathering, and further develop them. As in the previous step, facilitation is key to leading participants to overcome individual interests, work collaboratively and share their expertise and experience. If the groups wish so, you can also invite experts to meet with the groups and share know-how on specific topics which could be beneficial to the ideas' development. Once all participants agree on core aspects of a shared idea, and all of them have had the opportunity to contribute to it, it's time to start imagining how it could take shape. There are plenty of design and prototyping tools that you can use to support the groups in this phase. It is also important to test the ideas and collect feedback on them, for example through an open house event.

Objectives of the phase

- To generate ideas for solutions for the selected challenge and to make sure they are not only innovative, but also represent an added value for all those involved, and for the city overall (the common good and the mission objectives).
- To step beyond the obvious solutions and increase the innovation potential of the solution through co-innovation.
- To prototype tangible and concrete products, services, or organisational structures.
- To test such solutions (if time allows) by allowing users to experiment and interact with the prototype to assess the functions and scope of the product or service, providing a focused feedback loop for users.

The process

1. Ideation

- Ideation uses creativity and innovation to develop solutions to the challenge at hand. The key activities during this phase should help participants make random connections and brainstorm, to explore the problem in all directions.
- Type of activities: workshops where teams will be invited to use creative methods to develop new solutions.
- Starting from the results of the ideation workshops, participants narrow down solutions that offer more potential. This includes not only the potential to solve the problem but also its scaling-up capacity.

2. Prototyping

- During the prototyping phase, participants develop an early sample, model or release of a product created to test and be discussed by the different users and assess their features and usability. The prototyping phase can be divided into two rounds.
- Round 1: Development of lo-fi general prototypes of the solutions. Participants are asked to prototype the solution in its entirety with a low level of detail. Teams are also invited to identify what elements of their prototype are the most problematic or crucial.
- Round 2: For this second round, participants are asked to focus on crucial elements of the prototype. Participants are invited to test their prototype, by for example organising an open event with future potential users or engaging with them at specific locations.

What is expected from the process initiator?

- To closely follow and be involved in the idea selection and prototyping process, ideally by taking part in all sessions together with the other stakeholder.
- To be available to take over the outcomes once the co-creation process is over.

THE TOOLS

1. Example of co-creation general timeline

Step 1: Define the prototype.

- What is the core value of our project?
- What questions do we have about our project?
- How can we represent our project?

Step 2: Build the prototype.

- Use resources to start building the prototype
- How does the building change the project?
- What new questions does this open?

Step 3: Define the experimentation protocol (and finish the prototype...).

- Who are our users? When and where should we find them?
- Which experience of the prototype and the project should we offer?
- What are our questions?
- How should we gather feedback?

Step 4: Experiment with the prototype and gather feedback (i.e. open doors event).

Step 5: Evaluate your project through the feedback.

- What did we learn from the users' feedback?
- What strengths and weaknesses of our project did this unveil? Are there unexpected opportunities? Unexpected risks?
- Which questions does it open for the future of our project?

- How could we improve our project? Should we adjust it or transform it completely?

Step 6: Improvement of the project, depending on the feedback and the group’s progress.

- Articulate a new version of the project.
- Build a new prototype.
- Test with a different protocol.

2. Example of Idea definition canvas for participants

1. Basic objective.	2. Target.
3. Which information on air quality (which level of detail)?	4. Which Information on the Impact of Air Quality on Health?
6. Which indications for prevention?	7. How and/or where?
8. Value of the idea.	9. Other.

3. Example of Idea definition template for participants

The aim of today’s meeting is for your group to agree on an idea and detail it as much as possible. Here is a template that might help you do this. Follow these simple steps.

First, individually try to remember the ideas that appeared in your cluster. You are also welcome to suggest new ideas that fit your cluster. Write them down on individual post-its.

Choosing the first idea: We have to choose one of the ideas (not necessarily your favourite). As a group choose one idea that makes the most of this group, that reflects the multiple perspectives you are all bringing with you. Each of you will now speak in turn: you have one minute to draw the group’s attention towards one valuable idea OR one valuable element in this idea OR a new element that should be injected in the ideas. Have a discussion and try to agree on one idea. In case of disagreement, you can have a vote to decide the chosen idea.

Crafting the idea together: Each of you has now one opportunity to make the idea better, more precise, or simply to ensure that the idea is relevant for them. Each of you will speak in turn to modify one element of the idea:

- You can add an element.
- You can transform one element.

- You can give details about an aspect of the idea.
- You can raise awareness about a context, a constraint, something that has to be taken into account.

After everyone has spoken once, the idea may be quite different from the start... But this is now your common idea!

Detailing your idea: when you reached a consensus you may fill in the following template:

Who are the primary users of this? (don't answer everyone, rather choose the group who would benefit most from the idea)
How/when do they use it?
How does it make their life better?
What is special in this idea? Where is its core value?

4. Example of Idea definition facilitation guideline

0:00-0:10 – Welcome and introduction

Welcome to this new gathering and thanks for joining. My name is XXX and I will be your main facilitator today. Before we start, some housekeeping information:

- *(If food/drinks are available)* There is food available ..., please feel free to grab coffee, drinks or something to eat at any time. We have also foreseen a long break in the middle of the meeting for you to enjoy the food and get some fresh air.
- If needed, emergency exits are...
- Toilets are...
-

This meeting will be a follow-up from the Gathering. Today, we will agree on the precise idea on which the whole cluster will be working on. In the next weeks, we will use a process called prototyping to give shape to your project, articulate its details, and explore the opportunities it offers. We may even test it or dialogue around it with potential users and collect feedback. But this will come later!

For today, we will still focus on the ideas. We will bring back the ideas from last time and we may also explore new ones, but with one objective in mind: have everyone agree on one idea, on one common project. And we would like a bit more than the simple agreement of everyone: we would like the involvement of each of you in the idea, so that each of you bring their own perspective and experience to it.

0:10-0:15 – Icebreaker

Before we start speaking about the idea, let's wake up our bodies. I would like everyone to stand up. Now, I am going to ask you to scatter in the room as evenly as possible, so we have the best use of this space... *(Encourage them, draw their attention to empty spaces or people being too close...)*.

Today we will speak again about mobility, about moving in the city. Some of you live close to this very room. Some of you live further away. I will now give you precisely three minutes to organise yourselves and change places. The closer you live from here, the closer you should stand from this corner (*choose one corner of the room*). The further you live, the closer you should be from this other corner (*show the opposite corner*). You are allowed to speak, but NOT to use your phones, computers or other devices. No internet or GPS allowed! Ready? You have three minutes! (*Start the timer*).

(After three minutes: You probably had very different distances to go through, and used different means of transportation... Let's now use that diversity of experience for our ideas. Let's go back to our seats.

0:15-0:30 – Bringing back ideas

As you may remember, last time you were grouped by cluster. And from now on, we'll only be interested in your cluster's ideas. Do you remember the ideas to improve mobility that your cluster had identified last time? Let's take a few sticky notes and try to remember them.

We are going to write only one idea on each sticky note. First, each of you is going to do the exercise alone. Please write each idea that you remember, from this group only, from the Gathering. If new ideas came to your mind in last few days, or if a new idea is coming now, you may add these as well – still each idea on a separate sticky note. Now, let's gather all the sticky notes together, and spot what ideas we remember best, what ideas were almost forgotten, and what new ideas are emerging.

(Ask participants to tell an idea. Stick it on the board and ask if someone else had the same idea. Collect and group identical ideas. Underline any idea that was only remembered by a few, and if a similar idea is presented differently by several participants, stress the difference of perspective. Also collect the new ideas and add them on the board).

Some ideas may be more or less suited for this kind of project. Let's see a few principles that may lead you to change some ideas or to add new ones. Do you find that some of the ideas on the board are not ambitious enough? Then, how can you suggest another version, more ambitious, that really changes the way we do thing? Are some ideas too radical, or too ambitious? Do they seek to achieve something desirable but that seems utopic? Then, can you find ways to support the *change* towards that new utopic vision, rather than forcing the utopic vision immediately? Take a moment to look at the current ideas and suggest any new ones stemming in your mind from these reflections.

0:30-1:00 – Choosing the initial idea

Great, we have our bunch of ideas for this cluster! But now we need to work on one project for the whole group. This means that it will not be the idea of one of you, but an idea that is owned by everyone in this group – and thus shaped by everyone in this group.

It may be a bit uncomfortable, in many ways. If your favourite idea is here, it may not be chosen. If it is chosen, it will be modified by everyone here, so you may lose what you love most about it. However, the value of this kind of process is not only that we have a great project, but also that this project is grounded on a variety of perspectives, of experiences. The negotiation and the transformation of the idea by everyone is an essential element of the co-creation process, ensuring that we bring the whole complexity of this group into the idea.

First, let's choose the initial idea we will be working on. I insist on the word "initial", as this will merely be the first direction. Each of you is going to have 30 seconds to draw the group's attention to one idea, or to one aspect of an idea, that you find valuable. Use your 30 seconds wisely: please do not respond to other participants' views, just state your own views.

(Let each participant talk once only. If someone speaks 30 seconds, tell them that their time is up to bring them to a close.)

Thanks for this! Now, let's have a quick vote to choose our initial direction. You can all vote for one idea only: which one will you choose? *(To mark the vote, invite the participants to use sticky dots or draw hearts with markers. If it is a tie or almost tie, make a second round of votes with the two finalists' ideas).* This is now our initial idea. However, it still needs to be crafted by everyone here. But first of all, let's take a well-deserved break!

01:00-01:05 – Break *(may be reduced to 5 minutes if needed).*

01:05-01:40 – Crafting the idea

We now need to ensure that each one – with their own experience of the world - is involved in it. I will ask each of you to find one way to make the idea better. This can be:

- An additional element you add to the idea,
- A transformation of a part of the idea,
- More details or better precision,
- A context or something we should be aware of and take into account.

If you don't like the initial idea so much, then the question is: what do we need to add or change so you are part of it? If you like the idea already, the question is: how can we make it more precise, more detailed, more relevant? Each of you can add one improvement, and one only! Take a first minute, in silence, to think about the improvement you may bring to make this idea clearer, more relevant to you, more helpful to others.

Now everyone, will state their improvement: listen carefully, as the other participants' improvements may also be an inspiration for you. *(Have a roundtable of improvements. Rephrase the idea regularly so participants keep track of its transformation. Unless there is a big issue, this is not a moment for debate: it's a moment to see how the idea evolves and grow into something for everyone. At the end of the roundtable, if some participants are vocal about not liking the idea anymore, you can ask them what they would need to change and try to adapt the idea to find a common ground).*

(Optional: if you bring Lego bricks, you may do the same exercise where the initial idea is represented by an initial simple construction of a few bricks. Whenever a participant transforms the idea, they have to add some bricks (and NOT remove any). This is a nice way to materialize the process, add a bit of creativity and give the feeling that we are looking for a coherent "whole" involving everyone).

01:40-01:55 Writing the idea together

We now have an idea that is truly reflecting this group! First of all, congratulations, this was not an easy task at all, and you succeeded! Secondly, we now have our project settled, so let's write it not to forget it.

Invite participants to fill in the two templates which you can find in this Toolkit: the “Template for idea definition and planning further work (“Idea card”)” and the “Idea definition canvas” for participants. Mostly, draw their attention to the core value of the idea, what makes the idea “special” and different from existing services. It may be special for specific users only, or in specific contexts only. Depending on the time left, you may have participants draft answers for the first template only, or for both of them. If you still have time, you may invite them to start thinking about their team organisation, if they have specific roles, dates and times for meetings, tools (Emails, Google docs), etc.

01:55-02:00 Wrap-up

Thank you for your participation! We now have a clear view of our idea. The next steps will have us build a representation of that idea. Depending on the project, it may involve Lego bricks, the use of a Fab Lab to build a model, a storyboard to detail the way the idea is used, a movie that narrates the service... or other things, like the ones you see in the pictures of that slide. This will be decided together in the next meeting!

(Optional, only if you have enough time). Before we leave, I would like you to conclude this meeting with a few questions from you. No affirmation, no opinion, just an open question for all of us. We will not provide any answer, we will just leave each other with these questions. What question did that meeting open for you? What question may we share and reflect on? Whenever you want to, you can say your question. *(Questions are just said by participants, not written... Please note them for us.)*

Thank you, we will be in touch soon by email. We’re very grateful for your time and we hope you enjoyed the activities. Have a nice evening and a safe travel home. Bye bye!

5. Example of storyboard preparation facilitation guideline

Main expected outcomes:

- A detailed storyboard of the idea
- Integration of the “user’s journey” into the idea
- Improvement of the idea by adding “small innovations” to enhance the user’s experience.

0:00-0:10 – Welcome

Welcome to this new gathering and thanks for joining. My name is XXX and I will be your main facilitator today. Before we start, some housekeeping information:

- *(If food/drinks are available)* There is food available ..., please feel free to grab a coffee, drinks or something to eat at any time. We have also foreseen a long break in the middle of the meeting for you to enjoy the food and get some fresh air.
- If needed, emergency exits are...
- Toilets are...

0:10-0:20 – Introduction and icebreaker

General aim: In this meeting, we will start to give life and details to our idea, so it becomes more precise, clearer, and we may see new opportunities for innovation arising. Take a time

to remember what happened two weeks ago, ask them if they had new thoughts during the last days.

Objectives:

- To transform the idea into a clear and precise project.
- To design a first version of a storyboard

Icebreaker

But first, let's wake up! Find someone in the room you don't know very well, and make a pair. Now, think about that sentence: "in the past, I am proud I have made...". What have you made or built, you personally? A model of a plane? Your own house? A playmobile castle for a child? A knitted jumper? A painting, a clay pot? A paper origami? It has to be a real object you made whether it is a giant construction or a pasta necklace – you cannot say that you "build your marriage" in that exercise! You now have five minutes to remind each other who you are, what your name and your occupation are, and to share the thing you made in the past.

0:20-1:00 – Storyboards

Our first step will be to detail a storyboard of your idea. Have you already identified a typical user for your idea? Is that a 35-year-old manager? A 30-year-old parent with their child? A 70-year-old person living on the outskirts of the city? If this is not clear yet, take a moment to define together a primary user. Remember it does not have to be your only user, your idea may benefit a lot of other people! However, that person should be a typical user who will strongly benefit from your idea. This person is now our hero, and we will describe their journey and their story. *(If undefined, take a moment to clarify the user with the group.)*

Now, let's build the storyboard. This storyboard is a little story of how our hero uses your product or service, with several episodes. You are going to work in pairs. *(Make pairs, help participants if needed. The same pairs as the previous icebreaker would be fine, if you feel they worked well)*. Each pair has those paper sheets comprising a frame to draw and a few lines to write.

Let's start with the first team! *(Turn to the first pair)*: What is the initial situation? Before the user uses the service, where are they, with whom, in which situation? What day/time is it? What are they doing, where are they going, how do they feel, what do they need? It's up to you to choose a typical example that seems relevant. You may draw (in a simple, even symbolic way if you wish) the situation and write a few words to describe it.

Next group: your turn to add an episode. You can add an episode after this first one, or before – if you think something important needs to happen before. So, what is the first interaction with the product/service? Do they see it, hear it? Please detail the following episode of the story...

Next group: now, it's up to you to add an episode, wherever you wish: at the beginning, after, or even in between the two existing episodes. You can progress in the use of the interaction, or you can detail an element, add something to the product/service, to the way it is used... But it has to be described as one additional episode. For now, we are using these paper storyboards to take quick notes with doodling and a few sentences. After this meeting, you will be able to design a much prettier and more comprehensive one. You may take more time

to draw and write, or you may paste pictures from magazines or from the internet, and write your episodes with a computer.

Next group: what would you add to this story? Etc.

1:00-1:10 – Coffee break + Document

An important aspect that we need to keep in mind is that we need to document this process. We may keep notes and testimony from our works in various ways. You have here a Word document, that you may fill in during or after this meeting. You may paste here some pictures, add some videos or some sound recordings – if you prefer to speak rather than to write. But it is important that each of you leave an element, an impression, a memory from this meeting. The guiding question may help you to write a paragraph or record a testimony. You can already start doing this during the break if you wish, or at the end of this meeting, or later during the week. Please always write your name or initials after each answer, so we can see the multiplicity of the authors. To start with, take pictures of the storyboard to keep for later!

1:10-1:30 – Reflect

Take a moment to discuss the current storyboard. Is it comprehensive enough? Do you see opportunities to enrich it? In particular, are there elements we could add or change to make the service provided even better, to make the hero's journey even better? Sometimes, great innovations come from tiny details that truly change people's lives. Do you see any tiny detail we could improve here? (*Leave space if some participants wish to share their thoughts or reactions*).

01:30-01:40 Wrap-up

Thank you so much for your participation! A few things to do in the upcoming two weeks (*If there is extra time, use it for documentation*):

- Write answers in the diary, document the process as much as possible.
- Start thinking about this whole process described in the storyboard: where are the most important points, the most important elements? You can use the questions sheet to reflect.

6. Example of light prototyping facilitation guideline

0:00-0:05 – Welcome

Welcome to this new gathering and thanks for joining. My name is XXX and I will be your main facilitator today. Before we start, some housekeeping information:

- (*If food/drinks are available*) There is food available ..., please feel free to grab a coffee, drinks or something to eat at any time. We have also foreseen a long break in the middle of the meeting for you to enjoy the food and get some fresh air.
- If needed, emergency exits are...
- Toilets are...

Also introduce the maker space staff that will be supporting the group.

0:05-0:10 – Icebreaker (optional, you may skip it to keep more time for the tour of the maker space)

Before the session: gather a wide range of materials and tools from the maker space: a piece of cardboard, an elastic band, an electronic board, a wire, a screwdriver, other tools... There should be more materials and tools than the number of participants. Put all these elements on a table and ask all participants to look at them, and then pick up one material or tool.

Tell them to look at the material or tool they have chosen. What are its characteristics? Is it solid, flexible, cheap, expensive, precise, handy, sharp, reusable...? Tell them they have one minute to think to build their own sentence, on the model: "I am like this [material] because it is [characteristic] like me". For example: "I am like this wrench because it is adaptable like me". "I am like this nail because it is shiny like my my nail varnish". If they find no common point with their item, they are allowed to switch to "I am unlike this [material] because it is [characteristic] and I am not!!!". Have all of them say their sentence to the group.

0:10-0:25 – Tour and review of available materials

With the maker space staff, have a tour of the space: look at the various tools (laser cutter, sticker maker, 3D printer etc.), and most importantly look at the various materials: wood, metal, plastic, cardboard, textiles, rubber, electronics, wool, sticker, etc. It's important to show participants the diversity of materials and raise their "appetite" for manipulating and using these materials. Notice any interest being shown by participants.

0:25-0:35 – Back to the storyboard

Ask all participants to review the storyboards. Are there any thoughts that came to them since the last meeting? If there is a need to detail the storyboard a bit more, participants can do this now. However, you may also use the prototyping time to detail the idea. (Example: in the "Places for people" group, participants may find it difficult to define the activities available in the meeting place. But if they are building a model of the place, they may happily add all the elements they would dream about (a swing, a tea room, a ping pong table, plenty of books and comfortable sofas, Hi-fi for classical music, a dancefloor for pop choreography...). Building and adding elements to a visual model may be much more joyful and simple than having to imagine it all from nothing. Unless needed, this step should be very quick: a mere reminder of the service created.

0:35-0:50 – What will we prototype?

Announce the next steps: we are now going to build a prototype for the service they designed. A prototype is a simple, low-fidelity representation of the service, or of a part of the service. It will have us design the service in greater detail. Many different things can be prototyped in various ways:

- An object (with simple cardboard, or wood shaped by a laser cutter, or any other available materials)
- A building (through a model in cardboard, wood, or a Lego construction)
- An app (through wireframes, with a wooden frame imitating a phone shape, and paper to draw the various screens)
- Any electronic device or automated element (through Arduino, Makey Makey, or other elements from the maker space).
- A content or a programme (through a movie shot with a smartphone, using actors or toys/dolls for characters)

Ask them to review their service from the storyboard, and to **list all the various things that could be prototyped** (they should not yet worry about *how* they will be prototyped):

- Specific objects used in the created service
- Places and buildings
- Computer/Smartphone app or other interactions
- Signposts in the street, road marking, etc.
- Contents inside a hub or a building
- Organization of people (for example: if we need various actions from various kinds of people, we can model it using toy characters in cardboard, playmobile or other materials).

In discussion with the group, come to an agreement about which element(s) will be prototyped. should aim to choose:

- The element(s) that embodies the core value of the idea
- The elements that are critical to the success of the idea

Depending on the group dynamics, you may want everyone to work on the same prototype, or several small groups to develop several prototypes. This will also depend on the prototype: if it is quite simple, 4 people working on it is more than enough. If it is complex and made of several sub-parts, it may require effort from everyone.

Note: If participants are unsure about what to prototype, it is useful to come back to the question sheet (at the end of the day diary) and have participants reflect on some of the following:

- What does our idea need to be successful?
- What seems to be a critical element for the idea?
- How can we make it easy to use, simple and reliable?
- What could increase its impact, help more people, make it more efficient?
- How can we ensure people will actually use it?
- What part of the idea is likely to work well? Where will the issues most probably come from?
- Are there some ethical issues linked to the idea? Some social or political issues? Are there some acceptability issues?

0:50 – 1:50 Making

Next, you have to determine *how* you will prototype.

- **The materials**: With the help of the maker space staff, orient the group towards materials that could be used for their prototype. You may suggest a mix of classic materials (e.g. cardboard wood) and less usual ones (e.g. textiles, silk paper, toys, fruits...). Creative materials often open the imagination of participants, which is beneficial to the service created. If some people are attracted to specific materials (e.g. sewing), take advantage of it and try to make use of everyone's skills and tastes. Don't hesitate to throw in some funny elements to bring some humour and some pleasure to the activity.
- **The type of representation**: Try to frame the ambition of the prototype. Some elements will be complex or detailed (for example: details of the road markings, activities in the meeting place...), while others will only be represented in a very symbolic way (e.g. Colours to represent if a service is open or closed). A prototype too simple may be boring to make,

and a too ambitious one will discourage participants. If necessary, the maker space staff should be able to help you find the right level of ambition.

Have participants start making and building, joyfully. Your role will be mainly to check:

- When building the prototype, new questions will arise as it will force participants to define the service with a lot more precision. Whenever facilitation is needed, you may step in to frame a conversation, give space to a short debate or launch a quick brainstorming.
- If one or several participants are merely waiting on the side, try to “reactivate” them. This may be done by integrating them to the on-going task, or by giving them small side missions they will perform on their own, and add to the prototype at the end. (e.g. Design a sticker that will be made and added to the prototype at the end).

1:50 – 2:00 Wrap-up

Acknowledge together the progress and congratulate everyone for their work. The prototype is probably unfinished:

- Some parts may be finished at home.
- Other parts will need to be done in the maker space.

Plan together the upcoming work to have the prototype finished in the next two weeks.

Invite all participants to fill in the diary for today’s session. This should be done as homework - unless they prefer to do it right away.

7. Example of facilitation guidelines for feedback collection event preparation

Main objectives of the meeting:

- Finalise invitations of potential users of the innovation (groups are in charge of inviting people they want to get feedback from) - you can use a flyer for this.
- Decide who will present the idea and start preparing the presentation.
- Plan how the group wants to run the drop-in session (e.g., who will be there talking to people and how will feedback be collected?).

Introduction to meeting

- Summarise all prototype key aspects you have worked on so far, with the help of the group.
- Ask the group to reflect on key aspects of the prototype:
 - o Invite the group to reflect upon and collectively identify up to two key aspects of the prototype that could be important to further explore. Start working on them one by one, or split them in two groups if you have enough participants and ask them to focus on one aspect each.
 - o Key aspects of the prototype the group could focus on could include: a specific service, a business plan, a specific type of usage, connections with external elements that might impact the usage of the innovation, any critical element of the idea that they may have been forgotten, etc.

- If it can be of help, remind them the list of guiding questions we had provided in the previous script:
 - What does our idea need to be successful?
 - What seems to be a critical element for the idea?
 - How can we make it easy to use, simple and reliable?
 - What could increase its impact, help more people, make it more efficient?
 - How can we ensure people will actually use it?
 - What part of the idea is likely to work well? Where will the issues most probably come from?
 - Are there some ethical issues linked to the idea? Some social or political issues? Are there some acceptability issues?

Main working blocks:

About inviting “users” to the event / feedback collection:

- Do a quick mapping of specific target audiences that could be interesting to invite to test the innovation. I.e. supermarket customer, parents bringing kids to school, etc. etc. Think about concrete ways these people could be invited to the event and set up clear tasks on who invites who.
- Be clear that the success of the event also depends on them and that they should not expect “us” to make all the invitations and bring people. The city will do its best to help but they are also responsible for getting people to come to the event. They can invite friends, neighbours, colleagues etc. Anyone they think can give provide feedback on the idea.
- Plan other feedback collecting activities before the event. Explain to participants that if they wish so, they are welcome to organise themselves in going to specific places to collect feedback from people/audiences they consider interesting.
- Try to narrow down a few specific questions that the testing/collecting feedback should answer. Rather than “do they like it?”, it should focus on key aspects that could be improved or just better adapted to the audience.
- You can also invite participants to try and imagine possible questions that external users might ask them when looking at the prototype. Try anticipating questions and think of possible answers.

About presenting the idea at the event:

- At the beginning of the event each group will have 10 minutes to present the idea to the guests.
- Important: distribute tasks and responsibilities. Who presents? Even better if this is something shared by all.
- Some ideas on creating a presentation/pitch: <https://www.designkit.org/methods/create-a-pitch.html>
- The rest of the event will be organised on a drop-in basis, meaning that people can come whenever they like and someone from each team should be there to greet them at their table: present the prototype/idea, talk to them and collect feedback.

About collecting feedback at event:

Each team is welcome to develop their own protocol to collect feedback and will know which aspects of the prototype need digging into. However, it’s important to define your objectives:

start by clarifying your goals for the prototype test. What specific aspects do you want to evaluate? Having clear objectives will guide your testing process.

The teams are encouraged to be as creative as they like during the testing process, you might not only consider talking about the idea, but also showing visuals, simulating a user experience, role playing etc.

Questions one can ask the potential users

1. General Feedback:

- What are your overall impressions of the prototype?
- Did the prototype meet your expectations?
- Is there anything you particularly liked or disliked about the prototype?

2. Specific Features and Functionality:

- What did you think about [specific feature]? How well did it work for you?
- Did you find all the necessary options or functionalities you expected?
- Were there any missing features or functionalities that you think should be included?

3. Visual Design and Layout:

- Did the visual design of the prototype appeal to you?
- Was the layout and organization of elements intuitive and easy to follow?
- Were there any visual elements that were distracting or confusing?

4. Suggestions for Improvement:

- Based on your experience, what improvements or changes would you recommend?
- Are there any additional features or functionalities you would like to see?
- How could the prototype better meet your needs or expectations?

5. Future Usage and Adoption:

- How likely would you be to use this product or service in the future?
- Are there any barriers or concerns that might prevent you from using it?
- Do you think this prototype would be valuable or useful to others?

8. Example of facilitation guide for groups sharing in plenary session

Welcome and icebreaker

- Welcome the group and introduce yourself.
- Say a few words about where we are with our individual group work (starting to prototype).
- Objectives of the day: group sharing, receiving feedback from peers, thinking of the future for our innovations.

Ice-breaker

- Place 2 post-its of different colours on each chair (green and red or other colours that can be easily distinguished).
- Ask the group the following yes/no questions:

- Are you feeling energetic?
- Have you had more than 2 cups of coffee today?
- Did you take some time off for the Easer break?
- Did you get here by public transport?
- Are you happy with the way the idea in your group is developing?
- Are you ready to give some feedback to your colleagues from the other teams?

World cafe and group sharing on current ideas

10 minutes: Each group gathers around a table to prepare a short presentation of their idea and pick 2 people who will be the ambassadors and representatives of the groups.

15 minutes: Round 1: two representatives from each group stay behind, the rest move to the next table (clockwise). The two group representatives present the most updated and concrete version of their group's idea in maximum 5 minutes (be strict with timing). The "audience" is asked to write their feedback based on 3 questions: I like (what you like about the idea), I wish (what you think could be changed), I wonder (any ideas you might have for the group). They take 2 minutes to write their answers on post-its individually and there are about 8 minutes for a quick sharing session.

15 mins: Round 2: people move to the next table and repeat the steps above.

15 mins: All group members go back to their teams and the 2 team representatives who stayed behind, present all the feedback that they managed to gather. The group discusses.

Break

Vision of the co-created innovation

3 minutes: Introduce the exercise. The goal of the exercise is for the teams to think about the changes that will come about if the outcome of co-creation is to be inserted into the city. This exercise is done in the 3 teams (not mixed).

3 minutes: everyone takes 3 minutes individually to come up with as many post-its as possible regarding the following question "What will change at the city level (or urban area) if the innovation of the co-creation is successful by 2030?" It could be useful to have the question up on the screen or printed/written on a sheet of paper so that they have it in front of them.

15 mins: one by one everyone shares their ideas (max 1 minute each to present their post-its), they put them on a big sheet of paper and try to cluster them and get rid of any duplicates.

4 min: they vote and prioritise 3/4 changes that they find the most prominent and urgent to achieve to contribute to the sustainable mobility challenge of the city.

Wrap-up

If time allows, ask each group to very quickly report back (1-2 minutes) about the most important change they have identified and the most interesting discussion they have had.

Remind about the upcoming "all-groups".

9. Example of posters for exchanges among groups

mosaic

Fondazione Giannino Bassetti
for Responsibility in Innovation

Milano

Comune
di Milano

strenghts

weaknesses (and solutions!)

promotion

Mission-Oriented Swafs to Advance Innovation through Co-creation

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101006382 - H2020-SwafS-2018-2020 / H2020-SwafS-2020-1

10. Example of template for a narrative description of the idea(s) emerged

For each idea describe the following:

- Participants
- The idea
- Objective(s) of the tool/product/service
- Target
- Benchmarking (*What is already there, if and how it differs from the group's proposal*)
- The proposed solution (*including sources of data and information and description of the tool/product/service - you can also insert pictures and describe them – and technologies used*)
- Messages to be conveyed

If not described elsewhere, please also include descriptions of:

- Strengths
- Potential further developments
- Unresolved issues
- Possible promotion activities
- Estimated development costs

11. Example of Diary for participants/facilitators to record impressions during the process

DIARY OF THE DAY

This diary can be filled in during the meeting, or in the following days. The best is to fill it in through a shared document.

Photos

Did you keep some photos of the day? Add them here!

Diary

Please write a paragraph to answer each question. A different participant an answer each question, but please state your name at the end of your paragraph, to make visible the multiplicity of authors. Make your answers as personal as possible! This will be part of the archive of the process.

- What happened today? How did I feel about it?
- Was our project transformed by the activities today? What changed? What progressed?
- Do you remember a specific moment, event or anecdote from the session?

Questions sheet

- What does our idea need to be successful?
- What seems to be a critical element for the idea?
- How can we make it easy to use, simple and reliable?
- What could increase its impact, help more people, make it more efficient?
- How can we ensure people will actually use it?
- What part of the idea is likely to work well? Where will the issues most probably come from?
- Are there some ethical issues linked to the idea? Some social or political issues? Are there some acceptability issues?

12. Example of Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) for the management of co-created ideas' property rights

As a prerequisite for your participation in the (...) process, (...) intends to outline here below in a clear manner the expectations concerning the way in which those participating in the project should deal with information to which they may have access during meetings and group work within the project:

- You are required to treat as strictly confidential any technical information you may have access to within the (...) process provided by any other participant and not to disclose it to third parties. This does not apply to information that:
 - are, or will become, public knowledge.
 - are already known.
 - are or will become disclosed by third parties without this resulting in a breach of this Agreement.
 - are or will be independently and autonomously developed by parties who had no knowledge of the Confidential Information. Any such Confidential Information obtained shall not be disseminated and must be kept secure and confidential.
 - you are obliged to use the information provided solely for what you will be required within the scope of the (...) project and for no other purpose.
 - you are obliged to use the information provided solely for what you will be required within the scope of the (...) project and for no other purpose. This Agreement shall be effective from (...) until (...). The obligation to maintain confidentiality shall remain in force until such time as the information in question enters the public domain, unless breached by you or any other participant in the (...) project, and in any case for a maximum of 3 years. In case of violation of these requests, the participant will be excluded from participating in of the process and from access to the materials of the process.
- (...) commits to treat with the same confidentiality any information received from all participants in the (...) project.

Name and Surname - Signature (legible)